

**EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ACADEMIC
ACHIEVEMENT OF TRIBAL STUDENTS IN
SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF KHUNTI
DISTRICT, JHARKHAND.**

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Abstract

A person's life is full of various types of emotions. Emotions are very important and an inseparable part of a person's life. Emotions generate a lot of energy which may be constructive or destructive to life. In order to channelize this energy for the positive, constructive and all-round development of the person, he or she needs a special kind of intelligence known as emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize, assess, and control one's emotions, as well as the emotions of others, and even groups. Possessing emotional intelligence gives students the ability to make common-sense decisions, take intelligent calculated risks, and navigate difficult social situations. It also allows students to handle the added pressures of setting and achieving goals in an academic setting. This paper aims to study the level of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of tribal students in secondary schools, and to find out whether there is any significant difference in the mean score of these variables in terms of gender, class, religion and type of school and to find out the significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of the students. The investigators have used survey method for the study and took randomly a sample of 200 secondary school tribal male and female students of three different schools of Khunti District, Jharkhand. The sample consisted of students belonging to Christian and Sarna religions, in government and private schools. The investigators adopted and used the tool on Emotional Intelligence developed by Thomas Alexander (2004). For the academic achievement of the students, the obtained marks of half yearly exam (2017-18) are taken from the school records. For Analysis of data statistical techniques used were: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't'- test and Correlation. The findings reveal that there is no significant difference between male and female, class IX and X, Christian and Sarna tribal students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement. But there is significant difference between Government and Private School Students in their

emotional intelligence and academic achievement as Private School students have significantly higher mean score than the government school students. There is a significant positive correlation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of the tribal students.

Key words: Emotional intelligence, academic achievement, secondary school students.

INTRODUCTION AND RATIONALE

Education is a process of human enlightenment and empowerment for the achievement of a better and higher quality of life. Without this, life of human being does not operate. It teaches the lesson of humanity and is very necessary for every human being. Education does not mean to get specific skill and get employment. We say that anybody who gets education has developed from every angle. It means if we have got an education, we have developed in every field. Education can not only get in the childhood. But it is regular and continuous process. A human being gets education from his own experiences, even if there is no teacher for providing him formal education there will be education. When other person shares his experiences, at that time, a human being gets education. Education inspires good thoughts in human being. It is the education which carries human being in the way of success. With education, human being learns to use brain for taking any decision. Educated person contributes his knowledge for the development of society. With education, human being raises weak and uneducated persons. Education is a process which draws out the best in the child with the aims of producing well balanced personalities, culturally refined, emotionally stable, ethically sound, mentally alert, morally upright, physically strong, socially effective, spiritually upright, vocationally self-sufficient and internationally liberal. Without a teacher it is impossible to achieve these objectives of education. In other wards Education is a continuous and creative process. Its aim is to develop the capacities, talent in human nature and to coordinate their expression for the enrichment and progress of society, by equipping children with spiritual, moral and material knowledge. As education is the most important means for development, one can aspire to achieve good personality, higher status, position and

emolument through education.

A person's life is full of various types of emotions. Emotions are very important and an inseparable part of a person's life. Emotions generate a lot of energy which may be destructive to life. In order to channelize this energy for the positive, constructive and all-round development of the person, he or she needs a special kind of intelligence known as emotional intelligence. It helps an individual know and manage his or her own emotions, and others' emotions as well. It helps in making and managing cordial relationships with everybody in the society. It makes the life of an individual tension-free, happy, successful and prosperous. As a whole, emotional intelligence makes a person an honorable, respectable and a wonderful member of the human-society.

Tribal students, generally, come from the poor-rural socio-economic background with an acute poverty, lack of self-esteem, self-concept, self-confidence, awareness, aspiration and willingness to study. There are also lack of educational facilities and good study environment. Their rural socio-economic background affects their emotional intelligence, academic performance and achievement which in turn badly affects their future lives as well. In this study, therefore, the investigators make an attempt to find out the level of emotional intelligence of Tribal students in secondary schools of Khunti District, Jharkhand and its relationship in their academic achievement and whether it affects their academic performance specifically and their school-life in general. And this study may bring forth both positive and negative aspects and some serious issues and burning problems concerning their schooling, into light. So that, it may act as a help to the educational authorities to bring about an improvement in the education of the tribal students in the concerned region.

Emotional intelligence is the “something” in each of us that is a bit intangible. It affects how we manage behavior, navigate social complexities, and make personal decisions that achieve positive results. Emotional intelligence is made up of four core skills that pair up under two primary competencies: personal competence and social competence.

Personal competence is made up of our self-awareness and self-management skills, which focus more on our individually than on our interactions with other people. Personal competence is our ability to stay aware of our emotions and manage our behavior and tendencies.

Social competence is made up of our social awareness and relationship management skills; social competence is our ability to understand other people's moods, behavior, and motives in order to improve the quality of our relationships.

Emotional Intelligence can be categorized into two broad competencies with their domains or dimensions as given below :

- a. Intrapersonal Competence or Personal Competence
 - (i) Self-Awareness, and
 - (ii) Self- Management.
- b. Interpersonal competence or Social Competence
 - (i) Social Awareness, and
 - (ii) Relationship Management

OBJECTIVES

1. To find out whether there is any significant difference between tribal boys and girls of secondary schools in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference between tribal boys and girls of secondary schools in their academic achievement.
3. To find out whether there is any significant difference between Class IX and X tribal students in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.
4. To find out whether there is any significant difference between Class IX and X tribal students in their academic achievement.
5. To find out whether there is any significant difference between Christian and Sarna tribal students in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional

intelligence with personal competence and social competence.

6. To find out whether there is any significant difference between Christian and Sarna tribal students in their academic achievement.
7. To find out whether there is any significant difference among tribal students of government and private Secondary schools in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.
8. To find out whether there is any significant difference among tribal students of government and Private Secondary schools in their academic achievement.
9. To find out whether there is any significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of Secondary schools tribal (i) boys (ii) girls (iii) students (boys and girls).

NULL HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There is no significant difference between tribal boys and girls of secondary schools in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.
2. There is no significant difference between tribal boys and girls of secondary schools in their academic achievement.
3. There is no significant difference between IX and X Grades tribal students in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.
4. There is no significant difference between IX and X Grades tribal students in their academic achievement.
5. There is no significant difference between Christian and Sarna tribal students of secondary schools in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.

6. There is no significant difference between Christian and Sarna tribal students of secondary schools in their academic achievement.
7. There is no significant difference among tribal students of government and private secondary schools in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.
8. There no significant difference among tribal students of government and private secondary schools in their academic achievement.
9. There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of Secondary schools tribal (i) boys (ii) girls (iii) students (boys and girls).

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY.

The study is limited to only 200 samples of IX and X standard tribal students. The study is restricted only to emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

METHODOLOGY

The problem selected for the present study is concerned with survey type, the investigators have adopted the 'Survey Method' to investigate Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement.

POPULATION

The population of the present study consists of the Secondary schools of Khunti District, Jharkhand.

SAMPLE

The samples of the study consists of 200 tribal students in 3 high schools of Khunti District of Jharkhand State, from three high schools. 62 cases from Rajkiye High School, Jate, 76 from Loyala High School, Khunti, 62 from Ursuline Girls High School, Khunti. One of these schools is government, two are Private high schools. Random sampling method is used as the sampling technique for students and purposive sampling technique for the selection of school.

TABLE No. 01
Distribution of the Sample

Variables	Categories	Numbers
Gender	Boys	99
	Girls	101
Class	IX	113
	X	87
Religion	Christian	126
	Sarna	74
Type of School	Government	62
	Private	138

TOOLS USED

- i. The tool on Emotional Intelligence designed and developed by Thomas Alexander (2004).
- ii. Source for Academic Achievement ; the school record.

The investigators have collected the half-yearly examination (2017-18) marks of the students from the school records.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Mean , Standard Deviation, 't'-test and Pearson's Product Moment Correlation.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT

In the present study, general information data as well as data from the two different categories of respondents have been collected. The collected data were analyzed through SPSS and Microsoft Excel. Data is processed and analyzed by the investigators under the following headings:

- (i) Personal Competency.
- (ii) Social Competency.
- (iii) Emotional Intelligence.

- (iv) Academic Achievement.
- (v) Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement.

Null Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between tribal boys and girls of secondary school in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.

TABLE NO. 02
Tribal Boys' and Girls' Personal Competence, Social Competence and Emotional Intelligence

Categories	Boys (No.=99)		Girls (No.=101)		Calculated 't' ratio	Remarks at 5 % Level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Personal Competence	65.72	7.419	65.39	7.538	.313	N S
Social Competence	80.89	8.715	81.40	11.218	.357	NS
Emotional Intelligence	146.61	15.043	146.78	17.583	.076	N S

(At 5 % level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the table no. 02 that the calculated t- value of personal competence is (.313), social competence is (.357), emotional intelligence is (.076) which are less than the table value of t- ratio (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. So there is no significant difference between tribal boys and girls in their personal competence, social competence and emotional intelligence, This finding is shown in figure no. 01.

Figure No. 1: Tribal Boys' and Girls' Personal Competence, Social Competence and Emotional Intelligence

Null Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between tribal boys and girls of secondary schools in their academic achievement.

**TABLE NO. 03
Tribal Boys' and Girls' Academic Achievement.**

Categories	Boys (No.=99)		Girls (No.=101)		Calculated 't' ratio	Remarks at 5 % Level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Academic Achievement	209.22	47.679	214.06	67.516	.584	NS

(At 5 % level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the table no.03 that the calculated t- value is (.584) is less than the table value of t- ratio (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted . So there is no significant difference between academic achievement of tribal boys and girls. This finding is shown in figure no. 02

Figure No. 2 : Tribal Boys' and Girls' Academic Achievement

Null Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between Class IX and X tribal students of secondary school in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.

TABLE NO. 04

Class IX And X Tribal Students' Personal Competence, Social Competence and Emotional Intelligence

Categories	Class IX (No.=113)		Class X (No.=87)		Calculated 't' ratio	Remarks at 5 % Level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Personal Competence	64.98	7.456	66.29	7.449	1.228	NS
Social Competence	80.55	10.073	81.92	9.991	.958	NS
Emotional Intelligence	145.53	16.274	148.21	16.382	1.150	NS

(At 5 % level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the table no.04. that the calculated t- value of personal competence is (1.228), social competence is (.958), emotional intelligence is (1.150) which are less than the table value of t- ratio (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. So there is no significant difference between class IX and X tribal students in their personal competence, social competence and emotional intelligence. This finding is shown in figure no.03.

Figure No.03 : Class IX and X Tribal Students' Personal Competence, Social Competence and Emotional Intelligence

Null Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference between class IX and X tribal students of secondary school in their academic achievement.

TABLE NO. 05
Class IX And X Tribal Students' Academic Achievement

Categories	Class IX (No.=113)		Class X (No.=87)		Calculated 't' ratio	Remarks at 5 % Level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Academic Achievement	206.74	64.969	218.06	48.314	1.360	NS

(At 5 % level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the table no.05 that the calculated t-value is (1.360) is less than the table value of t-ratio (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. So there is no significant difference between academic achievement of class IX and X tribal students of secondary school. This finding is shown in figure no.04.

Figure No. 4.: Class IX and X Tribal Students' Academic Achievement

Null Hypothesis 5

There is no significant difference between Christian and Sarna tribal students of secondary school in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.

TABLE NO. 06

Christian and Sarna Tribal Students' Personal Competence, Social Competence and Emotional Intelligence

Categories	Christian (No.=126)		Sarna (No.=74)		Calculated 't' ratio	Remarks at 5 % Level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Personal Competence	64.90	7.465	66.66	7.375	1.622	NS
Social Competence	80.17	10.455	82.80	9.108	1.794	NS
Emotional Intelligence	145.07	16.802	149.46	15.218	1.845	NS

(At 5 % level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the table no. 06 that the calculated t- value of personal competence is (1.622), social competence is (1.794), emotional intelligence is (1.845) which are less than the table value of t- ratio (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null

hypothesis is accepted. So there is no significant difference between Christian and Sarna tribal students in their personal competence, social competence and emotional intelligence. This finding is shown in figure no.05

Figure No. 5 : Christian and Sarna Tribal Students' Personal Competence, Social Competence and Emotional Intelligence

Null Hypothesis 6

There is no significant difference between Christian and Sarna tribal students of secondary school in their academic achievement.

TABLE NO. 07

Christian And Sarna Tribal Students' Academic Achievement

Categories	Christian (No.=126)		Sarna (No.=74)		Calculated 't' ratio	Remarks at 5 % Level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Academic Achievement	207.51	59.342	218.74	56.584	1.315	NS

(At 5 % level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the table no.07 that the calculated t- value is (1.315) less than the table value of t- ratio (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted .So there is no significant difference between academic achievement of Christian and Sarna tribal students. This finding is shown in figure no.06

Figure No. 06 : Christian and Sarna Tribal Students' Academic Achievement

Null Hypothesis 7

There is no significant difference between tribal students of government and private secondary school in their personal competence, social competence and over all emotional intelligence with personal competence and social competence.

TABLE NO. 8

Government and Private Secondary School Tribal Students' Personal Competence, Social Competence and Emotional Intelligence

Categories	Government (No.=62)		Private (No.=138)		Calculated 't' ratio	Remarks at 5 % Level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Personal Competence	63.52	8.560	66.46	6.749	2.621	S
Social Competence	76.95	10.542	83.03	9.234	4.117	S
Emotional Intelligence	140.47	18.035	149.49	14.741	3.729	S

(At 1% level of significance the table value of 't' is 2.58)

It is inferred from the table no.08 that the calculated t- value of personal competence is (2.621), social competence is (4.117), emotional intelligence is (3.729) which are more than the table

value of t- ratio (2.58) at 0.01 level of significance. The mean scores of Private School Students (M = 66.46, 83.03, 149.49) are better than the mean scores of Government School Students (M = 63.52, 76.95, 104.47). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. So there is a significant difference between Government and Private secondary school tribal students in their personal competence, social competence and emotional intelligence. This finding is shown in figure no.07

Figure No. 07 : Government and Private Secondary School Tribal Students' Personal Competence, Social Competence and Emotional Intelligence

Null Hypothesis 8

There is no significant difference between tribal students of government and private secondary schools in their academic achievement.

TABLE NO. 9

Government And Private Secondary School Tribal Students' Academic Achievement.

Categories	Government (No.=62)		Private (No.=138)		Calculated 't' ratio	Remarks at 5 % Level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Academic Achievement	172.81	53.857	229.12	51.770	7.027	S

(At 1 % level of significance the table value of 't' is 2.58)

It is inferred from the table no.09 that the calculated t- value is (7.027) more than the table value of t- ratio (2.58) at 0.01 level of significance. The mean score of Private School Students (M = 229.12) is better than the mean score of Government School students (M = 172.81). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. So there is significant difference between Government and Private secondary school tribal students in their academic achievement. This finding is shown in figure no. 08.

Figure No.08 : Government and Private Secondary School Tribal Students' Academic Achievement

Null Hypothesis 9

There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of Secondary school tribal (i) boys (ii) girls (iii) students (boys and girls).

TABLE NO. 10
Correlation Table of Emotional Intelligence And Academic Achievement of Secondary School Tribal Students

Category	Emotional Intelligence		Academic Achievement		ΣEI&AA	Number	Correlation	Remark
	Σx	Σx ²	Σy	Σy ²	Σxy			
Boys	14514	2150016	20713	4556401	3105265	99	-0.100	NS
Girls	14825	2206963	21620	5083804	3288828	101	0.326	S
Boys & Girls	29339	4356979	42333	9640205	6241737	200	0.167	S

(At 5% level of significance at 198 df, the table value of r is.139)

It is inferred from the table no.10 that the calculated r value of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of boys is (-0.100), r value of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of girls is (0.326), r value of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of both boys and girls is (0.167). The boys' calculated r value is less than the table value of r (.139) at 0.05 level of significance. So there is no significant relation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of boys. But the calculated r values of girls' and both boys & girls' are more than the table value of r (.139) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. So there is significant positive correlation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of Secondary school tribal girls as well as students.

FINDINGS

1. There is no significant difference between tribal boys and girls of secondary school in their personal competence, social competence, emotional intelligence.
2. There is no significant difference between tribal boys and girls of secondary school in their academic achievement.
3. There is no significant difference between IX and X standard tribal students of secondary school in their personal competence, social competence and emotional intelligence.
4. There is no significant difference between IX and X standard tribal students of secondary school in their academic achievement.
5. There is no significant difference between Christian and Sarna tribal students of secondary school in their personal competence, social competence and emotional intelligence.
6. There is no significant difference between Christian and Sarna tribal students of secondary school in their academic achievement.
7. There is a significant difference between Government and Private secondary schools' tribal students in their personal competence, social competence and emotional intelligence.
8. There is a significant difference between Government and

Private secondary schools' tribal students in their academic achievement.

9. There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of tribal boys but there is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of tribal girls as well as students.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The 't' test result reveals that there is a significant difference between government and private school tribal students of secondary school in their personal competence, social competence and emotional intelligence. The private school students have higher level of personal competence (M=66.46), social competence (M=83.03) and emotional intelligence (M=149.49), than government school students ((M= 63.52,76.95,140.47). This could be due to the fact that they have high level of aspiration, self-esteem, self-confidence and self awareness about their own emotions and those of others, and skills to manage relationships.

The possible reason could be that they come from families which have moral and spiritual values where they grow emotionally well and have the clear objectives of life, well guided by parents. Private schools are equipped with better study and teaching facilities run by the Christian Missionaries, NGOs and Trusts, where they get a lot of exposures, experiences besides their hard labour. The teachers in these schools are well paid and they are given the opportunities for in-service training. They are made committed to their teaching work. They are given frequent workshops to gain many soft skills. They are emotionally and academically better-off in dealing with the tribal students. The tribal students learn their qualities while receiving educational experiences from them. The schools are well-managed, well-equipped and disciplined. Besides classroom experiences, the experiences of various co-curricular activities and opportunities are made available for the tribal students.

The 't' test result shows that there is a significant difference between government and private school tribal students in their academic achievement. Private school tribal students have higher level of

academic achievement (M=229.12) than Government school (M=172.81). This is because of the fact that in private school students have better access to computers, library and other center of knowledge. The teachers in the private schools are more committed and regular in teaching and they receive frequent in service training through seminar, workshops and talk by guest speakers. Private schools are well managed, well equipped and disciplined and good facilities are provided for teaching learning. Good study environment, lot of co curricular activities are done for all round development.

Though tribal people are coming up in different fields of life, yet they are still socially backward, economically poor, politically exploited, discriminated against, oppressed and suppressed; and educationally illiterate in India, specially in Chhotanagpur. Jharkhand is only a part of Chhotanagpur. The typical nature of the tribals here is that those who are educationally and economically well-off, do not at all bother about the less fortunate ones. However, with the passage of time, education is becoming popular here due to the selfless and hard labour of the Christian missionaries, efforts of the government and the equal educational opportunities provided to all.

In the present study titled "*Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Tribal Students in secondary Schools of Khunti District, Jharkhand*", the investigator has made an attempt to investigate the level of personal competence, social competence, emotional Intelligence and academic achievement of tribal students in Secondary schools and its relationship in their academic achievement. The study has revealed the average level of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of the tribal students which can be improved. Although there is difference in the mean scores of Christian and Sarna Tribal Students in their personal competency, social competency, emotional intelligence and academic achievement but it is not enough to reject the hypothesis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations which came into the mind of the investigators for the teachers, students, administrators and policy

makers are as follows .

1. In order to improve the personal competence, social competence, emotional intelligence of the students, sharing about life, group activities, picnics, tours, seminars, group discussions, cultural programs like dance, singing, dramas, sports and games should be regularly arranged.
2. In order to improve the academic achievement of the students, a good study environment, library, encouragement to study hard, coaching and tuition of difficult subjects, well-trained teachers, hostel facilities, opportunities for elocution contest and competitions in speech, poetry, mathematics and all other subjects should be provided.

It is hoped that the policy makers and the administrators will use these suggestion to enhance emotional intelligence and academic achievement of tribal students in secondary schools.

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